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METHODOLOGY OF TECHNICAL LEVEL AND QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL EQUIPMENT BASED ON QUALIMETRY IN THE THEORETICAL BASIS OF IMPROVEMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL EQUIPMENT

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Abstract: In this article, as a result of determining weighting coefficients according to literary sources and analyzing them, the author determines the most optimal and objective weighting coefficients of technological equipment for car repair in different working conditions from a mathematical point of view, in relation to the decisive task of evaluating the technical level, competitiveness, and efficiency.

Keywords: *expert method, method of coefficients, technical service, qualimetrics, hierarchical structure, property tree.*

The variety of technical level and quality assessment methods used in the industry for the maintenance of technological equipment of vehicles has two main approaches. The first approach is represented by the Profile (or cystogram) method, in which all the characteristics of the equipment are

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assumed to be conditionally balanced. In the second approach, the balance of the characteristics of the equipment is recognized and the weights of the characteristics are determined by expert methods.

There are methods to analytically determine the weighting coefficients of the characteristics in the main of the local vocational school. However, they are impractical in the transportation industry due to the complex mathematical apparatus and the difficulties perceived by engineering and technical personnel. The task of this department is to master them and put them into practice in assessing the technical level and quality of technological equipment for the maintenance of motor vehicles.

- Basic principles of qualimetry.

Qualimetry (Latin qualis - what, what kind of quality and Greek metro - measure) is a branch of science that combines methods of a quantitative assessment of product quality. One of the main principles of qualimetry is that the quality of the evaluated object is characterized by a combination of properties organized in the form of a multi-level hierarchical structure - a tree of properties. The essence of the problem is to find rules for building a property tree (that is, rules for successive decomposition of the concept of "quality"), with the help of which it is possible to obtain a corresponding property tree with a relatively low value. costs, taking into account specific assessment conditions for each assessment subject. After our task, we find a comprehensive indicator of the technical level and quality for each sample, and the same types are created for the equipment for the line itself. According to qualimetry, the set of characteristics that make up the quality of the equipment divided into the level of simple and measured characteristics. The complex quality indicator of the equipment K_{kj} is defined as an arithmetic mean:

$$K_{kj} = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_{ij} * G_i$$

Here Q_{ij} - simple characteristics of the equipment; $i = 1, \dots, n$, n - the number of features of the viewed equipment; $j, \dots, m$, m - the number of equipment samples in this line; G_i - weighting coefficients of equipment characteristics.

Since the values of individual indicators of properties have different measurement units, the values of these indicators are normalized:

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$$K_{ij} = \frac{Q_{ij} - q_i^{ys}}{q_i^{et} - q_i^{ys}}$$

Here, K_{ij} is the normalized (relative) indicator of the i -feature of the j -version of the object; q_i^{ys} – invalidity value of the i -indicator (a value smaller than this received line); benchmark value of q_i^{et} – i -indicator (the larger value is taken from the row in question). The final assessment of the quality of the j -version of the object can be calculated according to the following formula:

$$K_{kj} = \sum_{i=1}^n K_{ij} * G_i$$

Here K_{kj} is the complex quality indicator of the j -th object.

In the practice of qualified calculations, many methods of determining weight coefficients are used:

- expert method for determining weighting coefficients;
- method of statistical processing of projects;
- method of final and nominal values;
- method of maximum permissible values of indicators;
- system of linear equations;
- the method of specific correlation coefficients and others.

The most common method is the expert method. The main disadvantage of determining the weighting coefficients by the expert method is the complexity of choosing experts. Who should be involved as a decision-maker when evaluating garage equipment? Maybe a group of engineers? Or automotive repair and maintenance engineers? As with any combination of experts, the opinions of experts are inherently subjective. Therefore, it is desirable to use other methods that allow objective justification and evaluation of the weighting coefficients of the characteristics of technological equipment.

In the qualitative literature, it is emphasized that the expert method should be used in principle if the weighting coefficients cannot be determined by calculation methods.

Analysis of some analytical methods of calculating weighting coefficients (last and nominal values method); analysis of some analytical methods for calculating the weighting coefficients showed

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that they work with the products of the maximum permissible P_m and average P_{or} values $P_1 \dots P_n$. Determining the weight coefficient of the characteristics of garage equipment, the analysis of these methods showed that they can be used in theory, but because the values of the maximum permissible consumption characteristics are not defined, and their relationship with the level of quality is not defined for the type of production that is not taken into account. The rationale for these parameters is the subject of a separate scientific study, where these methods cannot be used.

As a result of the analysis of the above methods of determining weight coefficients according to literary sources, the author concluded that technological equipment for repairing and repairing cars is the most optimal from a mathematical point of view and objectively determines the weight coefficients of equipment in different working conditions concerning the decisive task of evaluating the technical level, competitiveness, and efficiency. There are two possible methods: the method of coefficients of a system of linear equations and the method of private correlation coefficients.

Conclusion: the theoretical foundations of improvement of technological equipment based on laws, scientific-methodical and theoretical-methodical approaches, including models, serve as a new theoretical basis for the improvement of procedures for testing and control of motor vehicles.

Experimental research methods were developed in order to ensure the achievement of the tasks set for the scientific justification of the directions for improving the quality of technological equipment for the maintenance of motor vehicles.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Ergashev.M.I, Nzimoddinova.M.Sh, Mirzatillayev.A.A. Анализ методических подходов к технической оценке уровня и качества гаражного оборудования при обеспечении технического обслуживания автотранспортных средств.

International scientific – practical conference on “Modern Education: Problems and Solutions”. Vol. 1 No. 6 (2022) France (31-35).

2. Nizomiddinova.M.Sh, Mirzatillayev.A.A, Xonkeldiev.M.A. (2023). Texnologik uskunalarni takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslarida “Operator - Avtotransport vositalari - texnologik uskunalar -

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o'lchash vositalari muhit" tizimini tahlil qilish. "Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot" nomli ilmiy, masofaviy, onlayn konferensiya. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7628875>. (36-43).

3. U. R., Tohirovich, Q. N., & O'G'Li, Q. N. A. (2021). Bilvosita soliqlarning soliq tizimidagi tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(10), 719-723.

4. Shaxrinoz .Avazxonovna Kurbonova (2021). Mahsulot tannarxi hisobiga olishda boshqaruv hisobini takomillashtirish masalalari. *Scientific progress*, 2 (8), 603-607.

